

Properties of Phenolic Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics

L. J. Broutman

Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Illinois Institute of Technology, 10 W 33rd St. Chicago 511, Illinois 60616, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

Phenol formaldehyde fibers (Kynol) have been compounded into various thermoplastic matrix materials using a twin screw extruder. In this paper, concentration will be on the physical properties of phenolic fiber reinforced polypropylene. Tensile properties, impact properties, heat distortion temperature and damping have been characterized as a function of fiber concentration, length and surface treatment. Unique composite properties have been achieved. In the case of polypropylene matrix composites, high heat distortion temperature can be produced without adversely influencing the low temperature impact strength. This is not possible with glass or mineral filled polypropylene composites. The mechanism of reinforcement and influence of surface treatment will be discussed.

